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Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mustafa Korumaz

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6337-9087>

Konya Technical University, Faculty of Architecture and Design, Konya / TÜRKİYE

ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02s82rs08>

Msc Arch Mehmet Özer

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9490-9271>

PhD Candidate, Konya Technical University, Institute of Graduate Studies Konya / TÜRKİYE

ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02s82rs08>

Evaluations on the Transformation of the Castle Settlement of Aksaray Province in the Context of Historical Urban Development

Aksaray İli Kale İçi Yerleşiminin Dönüşümü Hakkında Tarihi Kent Gelişimi Bağlamında Değerlendirmeler

ABSTRACT

Historical city centers are areas structured according to a traditional order and transfer the social, cultural, economic and historical accumulation of cities from the past to the present by reshaping and transferring them to our time. In the historical process, historical centers, where trade, traditional craftsmanship, public buildings, as well as residences for settlement purposes, are inadequate and cannot meet the needs due to rapid urbanization in our age. Today, urbanization due to increasing population, developing economic conditions, cultural change, different production and consumption habits cause changes, transformations and renovations in historical city center textures. Depending on the development of conservation awareness in our country, in recent years, renovation and revitalization projects have been carried out in dilapidated and collapsed areas of historical city centers in order to restore their lost original identities. In this study, evaluations were made about the historical texture built in the last century within the traces of Dışkale in the historical city center of Aksaray province. In line with these evaluations, the studies for the renewal of the settlement inside the castle were evaluated and the results were obtained that urban transformation practices that are disconnected from their historical ties will be incomplete in achieving the targeted success. In this context, in this study, first of all, the renovation works in the historical city center of Aksaray province, reuses and changes in the historical environment will be discussed with examples of applications in different cities of our country and the world.

Keywords: Aksaray City Center, Renovation in the Historic Environment, Revitalization, Conservation and Renovation.

ÖZET

Tarihi kent merkezleri geleneksel bir düzene göre yapılmış, kentlerin geçmişten günümüze sosyal, kültürel, ekonomik ve tarihsel birikimlerini zamanımıza yeniden biçimlenerek aktaran alanlardır. Tarihi süreç içerisinde iskân amaçlı konutların yanında ticaretin, geleneksel zanaatın yapıldığı, kamu yapılarının yer aldığı tarihi merkezler, çağımızda hızlı kentleşme sebebiyle yetersiz kalmakta ve ihtiyaçlara cevap verememektedir. Günümüzde artan nüfusa bağlı kentleşme, gelişen ekonomik koşullar, kültürel değişim, farklı üretim ve tüketim alışkanlıkları sebebiyle tarihi kent merkezi dokularında değişim, dönüşüm ve yenilemelere sebep olmaktadır. Ülkemizde koruma bilincinin gelişmesine bağlı olarak, son yıllarda tarihi kent merkezlerinin kaybettikleri özgün kimliklerini geri kazandırmak amacıyla harap olan ve çöküntüye uğramış alanlarında yenileme ve canlandırma projeleri gerçekleştirilmektedir. Bu çalışmada Aksaray ili tarihi kent merkezinde yer alan Dışkale izleri içerisindeki son yüzyılda inşa edilen tarihi dokusu hakkında değerlendirmeler yapılmıştır. Bu değerlendirmeler doğrultusunda kale içi yerleşiminin yenilenmesine yönelik çalışmalar değerlendirilerek tarihsel bağlarından kopuk bir kentsel dönüşüm uygulamalarının hedeflenen başarıya ulaşmada eksik kalacağına yönelik sonuçlar elde edilmiştir. Bu kapsamda çalışmada öncelikle Aksaray ili tarihi kent merkezindeki yenileme çalışmaları, yeniden kullanımlar ve tarihi çevredeki değişimler, ülkemizde ve dünyanın farklı kentlerinde yapılan uygulama örnekleri ile ele alınacaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Aksaray Kent Merkezi, Tarihi Çevrede Yenileme, Yeniden Canlandırma, Koruma ve Yenileme.

1. INTRODUCTION

Historical environments reflect the social, cultural and economic values and lifestyle of the past and are the expression of a great accumulation in terms of the relations between nature-structure and structure-human (Eriçok, 2015). Historical city centers are areas that have been structured according to a traditional order and have reached the present day by being reshaped under the influence of different identities and social-economic transformation processes (Eriçok, 2015). Historical city centers, which have developed due to rapid urbanization, developing economic conditions and population growth, cannot meet today's needs. As a result of rapid urbanization in city centers, negative transformations and renovations that damage the historical texture and do not provide integrity and harmony with the historical environment are emerging. Transformations and renovations made in accordance with the historical texture and with the understanding of sustainable conservation within the urban whole provide the revitalization of historical city centers. Within the scope of revitalization projects, many arrangements such as urban transformation projects, sanitization and reorganization of public buildings, facade arrangements, pedestrianization practices are implemented in regions with historical texture (Çetin, 2014). Re-functioning in historical city centers allows society to establish a relationship with its past culture and allows historical values to survive. In order to ensure the sustainability of the protection of monumental historical buildings, interventions that allow reuse in terms of ensuring sustainability require a multifaceted approach to be examined at the scale of a single building and its environment (Gençoğlu, 2018). Today, historical city centers are experiencing negative transformations due to rapid urbanization, and our unique urban textures are losing their identities due to the lack of sustainable conservation practices.

Aksaray, located in the middle of Anatolia, which has been home to many civilizations with its ten thousand years of history, has become a city of rapid urbanization and population growth since it became a province in 1989. Aksaray city center settlement and zoning plan formation are determined by the traces of the outer castle in circular form (Figure 1, 2). The historical features of the outer castle and its immediate surroundings, which have shaped the city center of Aksaray since the Anatolian Seljuk period, whose ruins do not remain today, but whose existence is proven in historical documents and researches, the changes and renovations that the historical texture has undergone are examined within the scope of the article. Although the Aksaray Kaleiçi settlement shares certain urban fabric characteristics with many historic city centers in Anatolia, it also possesses a unique historical development, socio-cultural structure, and spatial organization that distinguish it from other cases. Therefore, the decision support approaches developed within the scope of this study should not be directly generalized to other historic urban areas without considering their specific contextual dynamics. In particular, factors such as ownership structure, local governance policies, levels of public participation, and the physical condition of heritage buildings vary across different settlements. At this point, the morphogenetic development, spatial organization, street-building relationships, parcel structures, and stratified urban texture of each historic city center must be evaluated through detailed morphological analyses. Such assessments are essential to ensure that intervention strategies are adopted in a holistic, context-sensitive, and sustainable manner. Accordingly, while the findings obtained from Aksaray Kaleiçi may serve as a reference for settlements with similar morphological features, broader generalizations require comparative and multi-site morphological studies.

Moreover, Aksaray Kaleiçi offers an illustrative case for understanding the structural, administrative, and social challenges encountered in urban conservation and adaptive reuse processes. Fragmented property ownership, conflicts between zoning regulations and heritage values, and the limited involvement of local communities in decision-making processes are commonly observed issues not only in Aksaray but also across many Anatolian historic cities. In addition, unplanned and contextually insensitive interventions that disrupt the morphological continuity of historic urban fabrics threaten the authenticity and long-term conservation of these areas. Considering these shared challenges, the decision support approach developed for Aksaray Kaleiçi—when reinforced with context-awareness and morphological analysis—has the potential to serve as an adaptable model for other historic urban centers. Nevertheless, it is essential that any such adaptation be preceded by in-depth analyses of the unique morphological and historical identities of each site.

Figure 1. Castle trace and gates plan diagram (Parselsorgu, t.y.) **Figure 2.** Aksaray City Center Castle scheme (Topal, 2009).

The outer castle constitutes the historical city center and the center of Aksaray. The development plan of the city, like other examples of castle cities in Anatolia (Kayseri, Konya, Kastamonu), today develops to its outer peripheries by taking the castle form as its center. The fortresses, which include administrative and religious buildings, consist of defensive structures that surround the city with thick and high walls and towers. Today, there is no trace of Aksaray castle except for the remains of a wall northeast of Ulu Irmak. However, according to the existing ruins and the form of the city center zoning plan from the past to the present and the data understood from the physical texture, the existence of a circular planned outer castle can be proven. The diameter of the circular outer fortress is approximately 430-440 meters, its circumference is 1500 meters and the area it covers is 152.400 m². Evliya Çelebi gives some information about the condition of the castle in the VII century. Evliya Çelebi says, "...it is a solid castle with four corners in a large area, on the edge of a large river, right in the middle of the city. All its towers, bastions, dendants and battlements are not very high and are arranged symmetrically. The castle had no ammunition, but during the time of the Jalalis a granary was built to store wheat. Cannon shots are fired from the castle during the festivities in the city and during Ramadan...".

Another important factor shaping the settlement of Aksaray city center and determining the formation of the zoning plan is the Ulu Irmak stream flowing through the middle of the city (Figure 3). The historical buildings in and around the historical city center of Aksaray, the study area, were divided into regions and marked on the 1954 aerial photograph. The aerial photograph in question, which is the oldest identified image of Aksaray, gives clues about the building density, settlement development and green texture in the historical city center at the time it was taken.

In parallel with the population growth and urbanization in our country in the last 50 years, Aksaray city center has also been affected by change and transformation. Many of the qualified historical monuments built in Aksaray historical city center from the Seljuk Period to the Republican Period have been worn out and damaged over time. Important works have been carried out in recent years in order to regain the lost values of the works within the destroyed historical texture. In some of the historical buildings within the borders of the historical castle, restorations have been made within the scope of revitalization projects and environmental arrangements have been realized on a single building scale. As a result of the examinations and observations made in the historical texture in Aksaray city center; it has been determined that qualified historical buildings have been revitalized with new functions as a result of restoration applications on a single building scale in recent years. However, it has been observed that the landscaping of the historical buildings has not been completed and improvement works have not been carried out on the streets where they are located. Qualified new buildings have not been constructed around the historic buildings, and the criteria for new buildings in the historic environment have not been taken into consideration. There is no qualified pedestrian transportation network between the historical buildings outside the circular fortress trace and the historical districts in the center. Historic spaces within the districts are disconnected from each other and there is no physical and social continuity. The neglected and unqualified building stock in residential areas should be transformed into healthy, livable areas through urban transformation and renovation Works.

Figure 3. Historical building regions on the aerial photograph of Aksaray city center and its surroundings in 1954 (Erdal et al, 2017- Edited by the author on the photograph)

2. URBAN REVITALIZATION PRACTICES AND AKSARAY CITY CENTER

It is known that Aksaray Kale settlement is a city with historical depth and has an important cultural heritage in the recent past. With rapid urbanization, the original texture has been almost completely lost in the settlement area, especially for the historical castle, and urban transformation projects have been initiated in order to prevent the resulting negative construction. When these transformation projects are evaluated, it is generally seen that they are designed disconnected from historical data.

When Aksaray became a province in 1989, steps were taken in tourism, industry and urbanization. With the effect of rapid population growth, the city center has started to grow and alternative centers and residential areas have emerged. TOKİ public housing areas growing in stages in the north of the city, Organized Industrial Zone was established in 2001, Aksaray University, whose campus was established in the south of the city in 2006, have been the triggering factors in the growth of the city. These social, economic and administrative changes have increased the pressure of change on the historical city center. The first cadastral study of Aksaray's historical city center and its surroundings was completed in 1967, and the change process of the historical city center is discussed in the study on the sheets obtained from the Cadastral Directorate and the zoning plans made until today. There are zoning plans made on different dates for the Aksaray province. Urban protected area and Conservation Zoning Plan were determined in two regions in the city center. The bazaar and trade center within the castle is planned as an urban protected area in the zoning plan. The Zoning Plan in question includes decisions regulating the repair conditions of the registered buildings in the region and the new construction methods in the immediate vicinity. The covered bazaar, where the majority of the shops in the region are bedesten-type shops where sarraf and clothing/apparel stores operate, is an active and vibrant commercial center today.

The city is defined as an organized artificial physical environment where an organization that exceeds natural and primitive life mechanisms is settled and represented (Kuban, 1994). According to Hasol, in order for a settlement unit to be called a city, 'it depends on the predominance of non-agricultural production in that unit, the concentration of means of production and population there, and the increase in the degree of integration' (Hasol, 1995). Within cities, which we can briefly define as 'organized artificial physical environment', the areas with the most historical heritage are historical city centers. Historical city centers are

areas that have been organized according to a traditional order, reshaped with their changing meanings and different identities and under the influence of socio-economic transformation processes (Eriçok, 2015). Another important feature of historic city centers is that they are places where the historical and cultural accumulation of cities can be observed and felt with their building stock, urban texture and reflections of traditional lifestyles. From this point of view, the conservation of historic city centers enables the historical building stock to be seen within its texture and the social memory to be kept alive. It is important to protect historical city centers in order to help the formation of urban identity, to create a social attraction center, and to provide economic benefits to the city with cultural centers and touristic potentials (Çetin & Sönmez, 2014).

The protection, re-evaluation and revitalization of the centers of cities with historical characteristics are important in terms of transferring cultural heritage to future generations. Within the scope of urban conservation, there are efforts to make simple and essential repairs of existing historical buildings against physical, economic and functional obsolescence, to prevent functional changes in the buildings, and to preserve the existing social structure (Gençoğlu, 2018). Urban conservation is not seen as an untouched museum object of historical areas, but its active use, preserving the past and establishing its relevance to the present, bringing appropriate use to current needs (Gençoğlu, 2018). The aim of urban conservation is to support historical environments that are cultural heritage; to ensure the use of scale and design that integrates with the historical cultural texture in the planning of the regions to be formed by new construction (Gençoğlu, 2018).

An urban conservation work should be able to control the new development in the historical fabric and should include a feature suitable for the socioeconomic structure of the society (Yazgan & Erdoğan, 1992). The most important aim of conservation is to keep the historical environment alive by providing new urban functions through economic and social solutions instead of a passive understanding of prohibition and preservation (Arabacıoğlu & Aydemir, 2007). An active and multifaceted method should be determined to revitalize and reveal historical values and to ensure cultural continuity.

Revitalization can be defined as the revitalization of cities that are economically, physically and socio-culturally worn out, lose their function and enter the process of collapse by eliminating and changing the factors that cause the collapse and bringing them back to life (Türkmen, 2018). The purpose of revitalization is to revitalize the area and add it to the city as a whole by producing solutions as a result of identifying the sources of problems by addressing the problems experienced in areas that have collapsed and lost their function (Çatalbaş, 2011). In the process of revitalization and development, the original and qualified historical buildings in the depressed areas are brought to the city by essential repairs and new functions. Different methods and strategies are developed for conservation practices in historic areas. The main purpose of these strategies is to provide comprehensive solutions to the problems of the historic district in harmony with its original identity. Different methods developed by Cohen (1999) and White and Roddewig (1994) for conservation strategies are described by Erdoğan and Özkök (2017). The "conservation potential matrix" developed by Cohen (1999) envisages the identification and grading of the main components in historical centers and thus enables the identification of the problems in the centers in a concrete way (Erdoğan & Özkök, 2017). Cohen (1999), in the method he called 'conservation potential matrix', specified five components (criteria) that are considered in determining the level of conservation in historical cities:

- Distinct urban character and clarity of the site boundary
- Locality and sense of place,
- Interior space, proportions and relationships,
- Style and design,
- Construction technique and material (Erdoğan & Özkök, 2017).

In the study of the level of preservation in historic cities, each of these components is evaluated in terms of building and use, and as a result of these analyzes, the current level of preservation in historic cities is determined. According to White and Roddewig (1994), preservation work in historic districts should primarily involve the study of historic character/identity and past practices, and the reading of the preservation history. In addition, a holistic study of the historic fabric by analyzing historical *landmarks* and nodes, and the development of legal-administrative tools should be included in the studies. Within the scope of the research, a comprehensive evaluation of the historic center and its surroundings in terms of land use and growth trends, defining the roles of the public and private sectors, and formulating strategies for the

future (White & Roddewig, 1994). In conservation practices to be carried out in historic centers, it is important not only to preserve the historic buildings, but also to preserve the physical, social and economic identity of the place.

Today, revitalization projects carried out in historical city centers mostly include strategies to highlight the existing cultural heritage with the understanding of the contribution of historical and cultural heritage to the economic development of cities (Çetin & Sönmez, 2014). Within the scope of revitalization projects, methods such as urban transformation projects in historical textures, sanitization of public spaces, squares, improvement of streetscapes, sanitization of the facades of historical buildings, pedestrianization applications are implemented. As a result of overpopulation and rapid urbanization in our country for the last fifty years, social and spatial changes have been experienced in historical city centers. The reasons for these changes stem from the fact that historical city centers are multidimensional and continuous places in social, economic, cultural, historical and physical terms (Günaydın & Altunkasa, 2019). Again, the search for spaces suitable for the needs of trade and service sectors developing with rapid urbanization causes the importance of traditional historical trade areas to decrease. This situation creates a great pressure on the historical city centers and traditional urban textures of rapidly developing new cities, causing these areas where local identity and culture are experienced to either deteriorate or disappear completely (Erdoğan & Özkök, 2017). Today, universal values and laws have been determined in the field of conservation at the international level. The conservation vision of each country conservation policies are developed to document the social, economic and cultural levels of the cultural layers formed in the history of that country (Gençoğlu, 2018). Our country has also been included in the international agreements made in the field of conservation and many legal regulations have been made in this field. Within this framework, efforts have been initiated to protect and revitalize historical city centers. Especially in the last 20-25 years, urban renewal works such as restoration practices and street sanitization have been initiated in many cities of Anatolia under the leadership of municipalities and non-governmental organizations. In Anatolia, cities such as Safranbolu, Beypazarı, Odunpazarı, Kastamonu, Ankara Altındağ, which stand out especially with their tourism revenues, have become model regions where these studies have been successfully implemented (Figure 4-5).

Figure 4. Beypazarı street texture (Özer Personel Archive, 2011)

Figure 5. Safranbolu general view (Özer Personel Archive, 2016)

With the effect of the interest aroused in Europe towards Hellenic and Roman artifacts, efforts for conservation have started since the beginning of the 18th century. With the strengthening of conservation awareness, the first steps were taken with some legal regulations. After World War II, the idea of repairing and evaluating the monuments destroyed in European cities and transferring civilizations to the future started to come to the agenda. In this context, the methods of intervention in historical buildings, monuments and historical settlements have been transformed into a discipline with legal regulations.

In the early 19th century, Viollet-le-Duc's restoration works pioneered the development of the concept of conservation in Europe and France assumed the leadership of the pioneer countries in conservation (Çekül, 2010). Following France, the practices of protecting the historical environment started to give examples in Italy, England and all over Europe. Since the 19th century, France has started to be structured with central administrations assuming the responsibility of conservation. In this context, it defined the principles of conservation with the definitions it brought to conservation principles, the laws and expropriations that pioneered the establishment of the legal infrastructure. Under the leadership of French architects such as Viollet-le-Duc and Haussmann, the restoration and maintenance of all listed buildings were carried out with state aid (Çekül, 2010). Viollet le Duc used the word 'Restoration' for the first time in his 10-volume work

titled 'Rational Encyclopedia of Architecture' (Arabacıoğlu & Aydemir, 2007). According to Duc, restoration does not mean the protection, repair or reconstruction of the monument. The restorer should also put himself in the place of the architect who built the monument and complete the building within the stylistic unity of the period (Arabacıoğlu & Aydemir, 2007). During this period, the understanding of conservation by law was established within the centralized state system in France. The main strategy determined in conservation was to adopt a repair approach that respects the identity of the building, with materials appropriate to the tradition, but applied in a way that would not be noticed (Çekül, 2010). In addition to protecting monumental architectural structures and artefacts not only for their historical value, it is also aimed to reveal their social, economic and artistic values in daily life.

Italy, bearing the traces of the glorious history and culture of the Roman Empire, is one of the best preserved countries in Europe. Since the 1850s, a planning and reconstruction movement started in the capital Rome in order to build a modern city. In addition to the idea of building a modern city, efforts were also initiated to protect monuments and antiquities in the capital. In this context, the Commission for the Protection of Works of Art and Historical Monuments and Antiquities in 1863 and the protection law in 1865 led to the formation of a protection-oriented institutional structure (Çekül, 2010). Gustavo Giovannoni (1873-1947), who worked as a manager in conservation institutions and a lecturer in educational institutions in Italy, made great contributions to the establishment of the understanding of conservation in the country (Çekül, 2010). Giovannoni argued that the texture around historical monuments adds value to the building and therefore must be preserved. He also brought a new understanding with his ideas on the integrity of the settlement and the preservation of the architectural order. Giovannoni's views were influential in shaping the principles and rules of restoration, known as the "Carta del Restauro Italiana", which was adopted at the meeting organized by the International Organization of Museums in Athens in 1931 (Çekül, 2010). Conservation understanding and strategies in Europe, especially in Italy, were shaped in line with Giovannoni's views. Along with the capital Rome, Florence, Siena and Venice are important historical city centers that have been preserved as a whole and have survived to the present day (Figure 6,7).

Figure 6. General view of the of Rome (Sekban, 2019)

Figure 7. General view of Florence (Sekban, 2019)

Especially in the historical centers of cities, collapse areas emerge as a result of aging and wear and tear in the historical process. There are different methods applied in the world and in our country that will ensure the integration of the aging areas of the city center into the city by renewing them, increasing the quality of life and bringing them to the city. The concept of 'Urban Transformation and Renewal' is one of the most frequently used methods in the world and in our country in recent years in order to transform the physical deterioration and collapse areas in cities into healthy and sustainable areas with comprehensive urban plans. Different definitions are used to explain the concept of urban regeneration. According to the definition cited by Lichfield (1992), urban regeneration is the specialization on the findings to be obtained in the transformation to be realized, which arises from the need to understand and develop urban deterioration processes (Türkmen 2018). Donnison (1993)- cited definition of urban regeneration is the methods that emerge to produce solutions in parallel with the problems experienced in deteriorating urban depressions (Türkmen, 2018). According to the definition cited by Thomas (2003), urban regeneration is defined as a comprehensive vision and action to provide a permanent solution to the economic, physical, social and environmental conditions of a deteriorating and changing region in order to produce solutions to urban problems (Şişman & Kibaroğlu, 2009). In urban regeneration; a number of intervention and implementation methods are used in order to qualitatively organize the urban areas that have collapsed;

- Revitalization
- Cleaning

- Urban conservation,
- Redevelopment,
- Reproduction,
- Urban renewal,
- Urban sanitization,
- Urban gentrification,
- Improving urban quality,
- It has taken its place in the literature as rehabilitation and integration (Yaman, 2014)

In recent years, it has been determined that urban conservation revitalization projects in European cities have been carried out in four areas:

- revitalization of decadent historical centers,
- upgrading of historical centers,
- revitalization of industrial and commercial areas of historical value,
- Preservation of small and medium-sized historical cities (Akkar, 2006 as cited in Çetin, 2012).

In the historical city center of Aksaray, there are spatial differences especially between the Government Mansions and the 4th zone around the square. Zone 4, which is located behind the buildings on Bankalar Street facing the square, is a depressed area in terms of the building stock it contains. There are major differences in terms of building and street texture between the two adjacent areas. Urban integrity should be ensured through transformation and renovation works to be carried out between these areas, which are not integrated with the square and cannot be integrated with each other. Aksaray city center within the Castle 4. The old and worn out buildings in the region can be adapted by taking the Urban transformation works applied in the example of Barcelona, Spain as a model. Textural integration with the city square should be ensured with the area clearing and revitalization method, which is one of the basic methods applied in urban regeneration studies. Transformation practices with low building density that will alleviate the burden brought by the commercial center, banks and Government Mansions clustered around the city square should be preferred in these areas. The building heights to be proposed in the planning should be designed in such a way that they do not exceed the widths of the Government Mansions. In addition, transformation plans that solve the green space and parking lot needs within the castle should be implemented.

Due to the importance of Aksaray Government Square at the center of the city, the buildings facing the square and their façade characters are also of great importance. The ground floor of most of the existing buildings surrounding the square consists of bank branches, clothing stores and other units with high commercial value. Except for two buildings constructed in recent years, most of the buildings built in adjoining order are over thirty years old. There are façade deterioration and wear and tear caused by years of use. There are no regulations regarding the facade arrangements of the existing buildings such as facade cladding, signage size and coloring in search of visual integrity and harmony. Local administrations have not found any improvement conditions for the facades of existing commercial units. However, in historical city centers, especially in squares, facade arrangement practices that respect the existing historical texture are carried out. Arrangements should be made around Aksaray historical city center square for the facade visuals that harm the historical identity. In this framework, color and size limitations should be imposed for the add-ons that create visual pollution such as signs, billboards, air conditioners and antennas on the surface of the buildings facing the square. Additions that create visual pollution on the facade of the building should be removed, and color standards and harmony should be introduced through repairs to deteriorated facades. Different colors and facade coatings should be intervened to ensure color uniformity between buildings as much as possible. Integrity should be sought in floor heights and eaves levels in new constructions. The city square's surroundings should be transformed into a qualified character by means of rehabilitated and harmonious façade arrangements that highlight the historical texture.

3. AKSARAY HISTORICAL CITY CENTER REVITALIZATION WORKS

During the Anatolian Seljuk period, the most important determinant reference buildings of the historical city centers are the Friday Mosques called Ulu Cami or Camii Kebir. The Great Mosque, located in the northwest direction within the castle in Aksaray city center, was built in 1409 during the Karamanoğlu Principality period in its present form. Constructed of local volcanic tuff stone in masonry technique with cut stone and cross vault top cover system, Ulu Cami has been used for worship purposes until today. To the north of the mosque is the Provincial Public Library, one of the important educational buildings brought to the city by the Republican period in 1924. The body wall of the eastern facade of the Great Mosque, supported by buttresses, rests on the outer castle borders. It is observed that the transformation has begun to reveal the historical structure with the hollow areas created such as parks and square arrangements around the Great Mosque (Figure 8-9). This change and transformation continued in the 1950s, and it was determined from archive photographs that the space between the main entrance gate on the west façade of the mosque and the Municipality building was used as an open market area and a wheat/agricultural market until the 1950s. The area in question between the Great Mosque and the Municipality building of the period also served as a square where demonstrations, ceremonies and festivities were held on holidays. In the 1954 aerial photograph, the area, a certain part of which is used as a park, is the empty area of the inner castle area, where park-centered transformations took place until the 1970s. The road axis between the mosque and the Azm-i Milli Flour factory and Zinciriye Madrasah, which are among the historical centers outside the castle walls, has been open to pedestrian and vehicle traffic since the 1940s. Due to the existing commercial construction on this transportation axis, the road width of 10 meters has been maintained since the 1985 zoning plan (Figure 10,11). With the comprehensive landscaping and restoration projects initiated in 2006 around the Great Mosque, it has taken its final form that is used today. Within the scope of the project, improvement works were carried out by the Regional Directorate of Foundations for the ground problem of the mosque. Within the scope of the project carried out by the local administration, the school building used as a Girls' Vocational High School adjacent to the southern wall of the mosque was demolished and the area around the mosque was cleared. In the vacated area, low density building groups such as cafeteria and camellia were built with park and landscaping arrangement. By lowering the ground level in front of the main entrance gate on the west façade of the mosque, an area was created between the Municipality and the mosque for gathering and an open prayer area. The park and landscaping around the Grand Mosque is a qualified work as it brings the historical buildings to the forefront. However, the 4-5 storey blocks built to the north of the historical Ulu Mosque and Library building show incompatibility with the historical texture with their facade and gabari arrangement. Since no regulations and standards are set for building facade colors and signboards, it causes visual pollution in the historical environment).

Figure 8. The settlement around the Great Mosque in 1895 1907 (Erdal et al, 2017)

Figure 9. The Great Mosque and its surroundings in (Erdal et al, 2017)

Figure 10. Ulu Cami- Zinciriyé Madrasah road axis (Gül, 2020) **Figure 11.** Vehbi Bey street- 940s (Gül, 2020)

Government House and City Square: The monumental public buildings built between 1927 and 1930 under the influence of the National Architectural Movement were used for many years for Government House, Courthouse and Gendarmerie offices, and Tax Office services. The original third building, which served as the Tax Office when it was built, was demolished and replaced by a reconstruction in 1985 (Figure 12-13). Today, the building in the center serves as the Government House and the two buildings on the sides serve as the Governorate's additional service buildings. The eastern façade of the Government House is decorated with the Atatürk monument and the city square, while the western façade is surrounded by cafeterias and a hollow area. Today, the square is an open area where mass activities and organizations such as official holiday ceremonies, political rallies, concerts, festivals, activities of non-governmental organizations are held. The area encompassing the government mansions and the square is surrounded by Bankalar Street to the east, Tourism Street to the northwest and Ankara Street to the south. These streets are open to vehicle traffic and encompass the city square in the form of an island. The city square is the gathering center of the other three districts within the castle. No. 3 is the main artery (Bankalar Street) passing between the streets in the commercial area, the Grand Mosque and the Municipality. Located at the center of the pedestrian transportation and commercial center of the castle, the square and its surroundings, where three monumental public buildings are located, have undergone various renovation and arrangement works to date. The changes and renovations made on archival photographs and zoning plans are listed below in chronological order:

- In the 1940s, there was a single-storey mudbrick architectural settlement texture on the west side of the Government mansions, while there are hollow areas on the rear facades (west side).

- In the 1954 aerial photograph, it is seen that the area on the eastern side of the Government House has been transformed into a park arrangement and the area on the western side into a market area.

- On the aerial photograph taken in the 1960s, the government mansions and the historical city center settlement with its surroundings are observed. The large green texture and park arrangement on the west side of the buildings were destroyed in the 1970s and the Courthouse and Land Registry and Cadastre service building were built instead.

- In the 1967 image, the 3- to 4-storey building stock is observed on the main axis (Bankalar Street) reaching in front of the square, Atatürk monument and Ulu cami.

- In the 1985 zoning plan, construction decisions were taken far from the understanding of protecting the square and the historical texture. Commercial zoning plans with adjoining order and 4-5 storey Central Business Area with the legend "Central Business Area" were put into effect around the square. The high-rise and commercial planning decisions for the city center are far from the understanding of new construction in the historical environment and the understanding of protecting the historical texture. Since 1985, due to the increasing population, the density of the city square and its surroundings has increased and has become the city's power of attraction.

- In the 2003 zoning plan data, the commercial building texture around the square and Government Mansions was maintained. Renovation works were carried out in the historical square with ornamental pool and urban furniture and park arrangements.

- Transformation and renovation practices that emphasize the historical buildings in the City Square started in 2005. Within the scope of the project, the Courthouse and Land Registry and Cadastre Directorate buildings located to the west of the Historic Government House and its annexes were demolished. An underground parking lot and landscaping, pool and park arrangement were built on the opened area. In addition, at the western end of the area, a single-storey modern steel material was used to emphasize the period and material difference with a contrasting application to the historical texture. With the city square arrangement project, the existing pools were removed and the area was expanded. The Atatürk monument was transferred from the front of the Government House to the north of the square, which is the dominant point of the area. Some of the existing trees and green texture surrounding the square were removed within the framework of the area arrangement. The application was criticized during the period for being a transformation that is based on hard ground and aims to create a pure void. Emphasizing the perception of the square, the sphere object in a steel frame, built with contrasting materials and forms with the historical buildings, was placed to the south of the square.

- In 2014, the restoration of the Government House Building was carried out by the Special Provincial Administration and the building was ensured to be passed on to future generations.

- The last change that has survived in the city square was made in 2015. Within the scope of the arrangement, the steel sphere was removed and replaced with a clock tower made of today's materials. Urban furniture was renewed in the square and regional landscaping arrangements were made.

The renovation works carried out in the last fifty years in the historical city center, which includes the monumental Government Mansion and the City Square, which is the symbol of Aksaray Province, are mentioned above. The arrangements made for the protection of the square and the monumental Government Mansions buildings together have been mentioned. However, most of the buildings built around the square in the historical process consist of 3-4 storey buildings dating back to the 1970s. Since the facade improvement, signboard color and size restrictions have not been made for the facades of these buildings facing the square, they create visual pollution. It has been determined that there is no successful conservation approach since the mass and facade layouts of the buildings in and around the square, where the monumental monuments located at the center of the castle, do not meet the criteria for new buildings in the historical environment.

Figure 12. Government House in 1940s (Municipality of Aksaray Archive, 1940)

Figure 13. A: Government House, B: Courthouse and Gendarmerie Office, C: Tax Office ((Municipality of Aksaray Archive, 1956)

Trade Center: Trade and related bazaars and markets have a very important place in the centers of Islamic cities. Trade is generally concentrated in and around the Great Mosque. In Anatolian Seljuk and Ottoman cities, trade-related settlements, bedestens, inns and markets were clustered around central mosques called Ulu Cami or Camii Kebir. The city center is the most convenient place where people can comfortably and easily obtain and access their needs and where sellers can sell their goods (Figure 14-15). It is seen in archive photographs that trade in Aksaray is realized through markets established at various times in open and closed bazaars. In the historical city center of Aksaray during the Seljuk and Karamanoğlu Principality periods; 1 bedesten, 2 inns, 7 bazaars and 2 markets can be identified (Konyalı, 1974). The Kılıç Arslan II inn, one of the inner city inns of the Seljuk period, was located to the west of the trade zone in the 3rd Region, in the middle of the Ulucami- Zinciriye Madrasah road axis. The inn built by Kılıç Arslan II was characterized by the names Pembe Han, Pamuk Han, Butchers' inn or closed inn among the people (Gül, 2020). There were butchers, vegetable sellers and oil-cheese sales shops in the inn, which had a plan scheme close to square with a courtyard in the middle. In the 1985 zoning plan, the historical structure was not preserved and instead,

a trade with a height of H:15.50 meters was proposed. The building, which is one of the examples of commercial inns in the city center, was demolished by Aksaray Municipality in 1987 and replaced by the Municipality Service Building used by Medaş. The square-planned, 5-storey building built in place of the Seljuk Han, one of the last remaining historical buildings in the city center, has a negative impact on the silhouette of the historical city center with its huge mass and form.

The trade zone shown in Zone No. 3 is an urban conservation area in the current zoning plan. The area located between the Grand Mosque and the Government mansions and the square is today named as Government Streets No. 1,2,3,4. From the 1985 zoning plan until today, the area has been planned as a Central Business area with 3-4 storeys in adjoining order in all of the plans made until today. The settlement in the commercial zone consists of adjacent order bedesten style shops in the north-south direction. The streets where the shops in the bazaar center are located were covered with a polycarbonate vault system in the early 2000s and turned into a covered bazaar. The streets planned on a total of 15 islands are planned in a linear street texture with a width of 6 to 10 meters, cutting each other perpendicularly. It consists of around 200 parcels ranging from 5 m² to 690 m². Today, the majority of the closed bazaar is made up of sarrafs, but also texting and apparel stores continue to operate. The main factor determining the formation of the plan is the main road axis (Bankalar Street) in the direction of the square and Kurşunlu Mosque in front of the Great Mosque and the Municipality in the north-south direction inside the castle. The covered bazaar area has preserved its characteristic of being a center with a commercial function in the historical process from the past to the present. In the 1960s, most of the workplaces in the bazaar in question consisted of traditional shops with one or two floors. There are a few registered single-storey shops in the bazaar that preserve the traditional texture and have survived to the present day. The single-storey shops facing Bankalar Street have been transformed into business centers ranging from 4 to 5 floors. Today, with the modern showcases of the sarrafs in the bazaar and the garment stores, the historical quality has been lost and the area has gained the appearance of a modern covered bazaar.

Figure 14. Aerial photograph of the Trade Zone in 1954 (Aksaray Municipality Archive)

Figure 15. Entrances to the Trade Zone from the city square, 1950. (Gül, 2012)

Residential areas in the historical city center: Within the castle walls where the historical city center of Aksaray is located, there are two neighborhoods with traditional houses for archival settlement. Hamidiye neighborhood and Zincirli neighborhood are still used for settlement purposes today. The boundaries of the Hamidiye neighborhood start at the end of the park south of the Great Mosque and cover the area adjacent to the trace of the castle walls to the east. The area starting behind the current Municipality building and surrounded by the castle walls to the west includes the Zincirli Neighborhood. According to 1954 aerial photographs and 1967 cadastral data, archival photographs show the nature of the residential area with low-rise and courtyard houses within the traditional street texture in these neighborhoods. The settlement and street formation of the Hamidiye neighborhood reflects the general character of the castle. The streets run along the north-south axis and the parcels are located in the east-west direction. Depending on the increasing population and the growing city center, the neighborhood has started to deteriorate and wear out over time. Physical wear and tear and transportation problems have emerged as a result of the adjacent 3-4 storey buildings on the narrow street texture within the region. The area, where there are no social reinforcement areas such as parking lots and green areas, where physical facilities are inadequate, and which contains neglected building stocks, has turned into a collapse area today. Most of the spaces planned for workplace purposes on the ground floors of the buildings are used for storage purposes. The original property owners living in the neighborhoods have left the area in recent years due to the inadequacy and poor physical

facilities in the area. The area has turned into a cheap housing area preferred mostly by minorities and refugees. The urban fabric in question, which does not offer healthy, livable physical conditions today, should be revitalized and transformed through comprehensive urban transformation projects to be prepared by local governments.

The Zinciriye neighborhood behind the municipality building has a street texture in the northeast-southwest direction due to the topography. Today, the street texture and building stock in this neighborhood have the same characteristics as the Hamidiye neighborhood. In the historical process, the region, where qualified residences preferred by tradesmen due to its proximity to Ulu Mosque and the trade center, has started to deteriorate since the beginning of the 1990s. Due to its narrow street texture, inadequate social infrastructure, and 3-4 storey zoning conditions, the area has lost its attractiveness in the city center (Figure 14-15-16). Real property owners with middle and upper income groups have left the area, and the vacated houses have turned into residential areas where low-income immigrants and minorities reside. The ground floors of the buildings in the area consist of warehouses or unused, neglected empty shops like the Hamidiye Neighborhood. The neighborhood has turned into a slum and slum area with unqualified, unhealthy construction conditions.

4. NEW HOUSING PROCESSES IN HISTORICAL CITY CENTER OF AKSARAY

The zoning plan prepared in 1985 for the neighborhoods covering these areas removed the existing residential texture and replaced it with 3-4 storey commercial areas with adjoining layout. In the 2003 and 2012 zoning plans, no changes were made for the aforementioned areas, and the existing construction conditions were taken into consideration. With the zoning plan amendments, commercial areas were proposed for the entire city center. It could not bring an approach that protects the unity of trade in the historic city center and the surrounding residential texture in a holistic manner. As a result of the dense construction of 3-4 storeys in the city center, transportation, traffic and parking problems have arisen.

Figure 15. 4th District (south of Ulu Cami) street texture in 1954 (Gül, 2020)

Figure 16. Aerial photograph of Hamidiye neighborhood 1950s (Gül, 2020)

Figure 17. 4th District (Google Maps, 2021)

Figure 18. Hamidiye Neighborhood today's street texture (Özer Persomel Archive, 2022)

Especially after 1950, a rapid and negative transformation of Aksaray city center started with rapid urbanization efforts. In these years, low density residential and commercial buildings of Kaleiçi settlement were demolished and replaced by high-rise apartment blocks. The results of negative urban development in Turkey can be seen as a result of natural disasters. After the 1999 earthquakes, the concept of urban regeneration has become established in our country, especially efforts to build earthquake-resistant cities have started. Some of these studies were carried out in historical environments and an example of this can be given as Aksaray Hamidiye neighborhood housing area.

When the transformation works carried out in this area are observed:

- The urban texture was created without considering the morphological process of Aksaray,
- Where historical traces have been completely erased,
- Failure to integrate with the historical texture in terms of cultural scale and proportion,
- Local architectural tradition is ignored,

A design approach that prioritizes the interests of holders over cultural concerns has not been observed (Figure 19,20,21).

Figure 19. Hamidiye Neighborhood urban transformation blocks (Aksaray Municipality, 2024)

Figure 20. Hamidiye Neighborhood urban transformation blocks (Authors Personel Archive, 2024)

Figure 21. Hamidiye Neighborhood urban transformation blocks (Authors Personel Archive, 2024)

5. CONCLUSIONS

Historical city centers are the areas that transfer the physical and historical accumulation of cities from the past to the present by reshaping and transferring them to our time. In the historical process, these areas are worn out and collapsed due to rapid urbanization and population growth. Depending on the development of conservation awareness in our country, in recent years, renovation and revitalization projects have been carried out in the collapsed areas of historical city centers in order to restore the original urban identities they have lost. Since the 1970s, cities with historical and cultural heritage have initiated conservation, renovation, urban transformation and revitalization practices. Aksaray historical city center, which has hosted many civilizations with its ten thousand years of historical past, has monumental, historical and cultural values that

need to be preserved and revitalized. In this study, the area within the traces of the outer castle, which determines the plan formation in the historical city center of Aksaray province, whose existence is proven in historical documents but does not exist today, is discussed. Renovation works and application examples, conservation policies, new functions and revitalization applications given to the historical buildings with the arrangements made in the historical city center, which includes the area in question, have been discussed in the period from 1950s to the present day. The historical center within the castle was divided into four regions according to the functions of use. The registered historical buildings and the buildings around them, street textures, urban arrangements, changes and transformations experienced by the city center were evaluated on zoning plans and visuals. The adaptability of the implementation methods for conservation and revitalization in different cities of the world to Aksaray city center was discussed.

Evaluations, suggestions and research findings regarding the renovation works carried out in Aksaray historical city center are presented below:

-1. The Historic Great Mosque, the Library building and the park within the area covering the District have undergone significant changes since the early 1900s. The park, which reveals two historical buildings, should be preserved and the renovation works carried out on the axis of landscaping with green areas should be continued. However, the façade arrangement of the 4-5 storey buildings starting from the northern enclosure wall of the Library building shows incompatibility with the historical texture. Local administrations should introduce regulations and standards for the exterior colors and signboards of the buildings in order to seek harmony with the historical texture.

-The Government Mansion, located at the center of the city center, was restored in 20 years. The additional service building to the south of the Government Mansion, which was used as the Courthouse and Gendarmerie Office in the first construction period, should also be restored.

- Despite the restoration practices for the monumental monuments within the borders of the castle, the construction of high-rise new buildings in all of the above-mentioned areas within the historical area could not be prevented and the original architectural texture could not be preserved. No work has been carried out at the scale of the zoning plan and in practice for the new building criteria to be made within the historical building zone.

Until the 1980s, zoning plan studies were not carried out to protect the historical inner-city inns, which were protected until the 1980s, and they were replaced by 4-5 storey commercial constructions that would disrupt the silhouette of the city center.

- In the city center, zoning plans prepared within the framework of construction decisions based on the use of high-rise, contiguous parcels were realized. This has resulted in social, physical and economic obsolescence in traditional centers, deterioration in the texture and loss of the authenticity of the city identity (Bal, 2009- as cited in Erdoğan& Özkök, 2017).

- Except for the Government Mansion and the Great Mosque, there are no places within the castle that show the characteristics of historical texture. Outside the castle walls, there are areas of historical buildings that preserve their originality, have been repaired and revitalized. There is the Eğri Minaret Mosque and the Seljuk baths, which have been repaired, around the Ulu Irmak stream to the north east of the Ulu Mosque. In addition, Zinciriye Madrasah and Azm-i Milli Flour Factory adjacent to the castle walls to the west of the city center have historical and monumental features. However, there is no integration between these buildings and the focal point of the castle, the Government House and the square. A qualified pedestrian transportation network, guiding corridor and infrastructure to ensure continuity between historical centers should be established.

-The existing transportation network in the city center should be planned with a predominance of pedestrian routes.

- Zone 2 includes the Government Mansions and the Square, which is the commercial and social focal point of the city. Due to its historical importance, the buildings facing the Square and their façade characters are also of great importance. The facades of the buildings that create visual pollution and wear and tear around the city square should be arranged, additions should be removed, color standards and harmony should be brought with repairs to the deteriorated facades. In this framework, restrictions should be imposed on the additions that create visual pollution such as signs, billboards, air conditioners and antennas on the surface of the buildings facing the square. Integrity should be sought in floor heights and eaves levels in new

constructions. With harmonious façade arrangements that emphasize the historical texture, the surroundings of the city square should be transformed into a qualified character.

-3. The few registered shops remaining in the existing commercial fabric in the area should be repaired and protected. Uncontrolled and unsupervised construction and repairs should be prevented in the region within the scope of the urban protected area. For the poorly maintained shop fronts in the covered bazaar, harmony should be sought, even if limited, by taking into account the existing texture.

- No. 4. Renewal and transformation works should be initiated for the old and worn out collapsed areas in the areas covering both regions. However, it has been observed that this transformation is disconnected from the historical context. Successful urban transformation models in the world and in our country should be taken as an example and adapted to this region. The area that has turned into a depressed area should be renewed with the area cleaning and revitalization method, which is one of the basic methods applied in urban transformation studies. Transformation practices with low building density that will alleviate the commercial density around the city square should be preferred in these areas. In addition, transformation plans that solve the green space and parking lot needs within the castle should be implemented.

As a result of the examinations and observations made in the historical texture in Aksaray city center; it has been determined that qualified historical monuments have been revived with new functions as a result of restoration applications at the scale of a single building in recent history. However, it has been observed that the landscaping of the historical buildings has not been completed and improvement works have not been carried out on the streets where they are located. Qualified new buildings have not been constructed around the historic buildings, and the criteria for new buildings in the historic environment have not been taken into consideration. There is no qualified pedestrian transportation network between the historical buildings outside the circular fortress trail and the historical districts in the center. Historic spaces within the zones are disconnected from each other and there is no physical and social continuity. The neglected and unqualified building stock in residential areas should be transformed into healthy, livable areas through urban transformation and renovation works.

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All authors contributed equally to the article. There is a conflict of interest with the Mehmet ÖZER and Mustafa KORUMAZ named

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